

MATERIAL DESIGN AND RELIABILITY OF ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Keywords: material design, reliability, glass fibre, non-crimp fabric.

ABSTRACT

Wind turbine rotor blades are by far the largest composite structures made, and the 100 meter limit for a single blade is not years away. The blades are traditionally manufactured using VARTM techniques with continuous glass fibres arranged in a fabric and embedded in a polymer resin. The design process of these large and advanced structures is a complicated engineering accomplishment running across several disciplines. Nowadays blade engineers must not only master hard-core traditional disciplines like calculus and physics, but also manage other disciplines like economy, manufacturing processes, supply chains, quality assessment and reliability.

Quality and reliability are of crucial importance to deliver a consistent product to the customer, and are a consequence of all the remaining disciplines. For instance, imagine how to ensure the material quality of around 100 tons of glass fibres each single day - globally? This requires special attention and knowledge within all disciplines, not only regarding material science. One may also add non-material related factors like political decisions and willingness, local sourcing regulations, cultural differences, crossing borders and cost. As a leading player in the blade business, LM Wind Power is faced with these challenges every day without failing to deliver the same quality product to the customer.

With basis in glass fibres and non-crimp fabrics used for the main load-carrying beam of a wind turbine rotor blade, the following paper addresses the design and reliability aspects of these advanced composite materials. Quality assessment and challenges of the single filament through the fabric design are presented and discussed with industrial examples.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites are the natural material selection for wind turbine rotor blades due to their large strength and stiffness to weight ratio (specific property) compared to conventional structural materials [1,2]. During the recent decades, the rotor blade size development has increased rapidly as illustrated in Fig. 1. In turn, much effort has been put on the improvement of the mechanical properties and the reliability of these composite materials in order to reduce the blade weight by materials savings.

Figure 1: Size development of LM Wind Power blades during the last decades. The number LM XX denotes the blade length in meters, and the number below the associated electrical power output from the turbine.

The processed composite in the blade main laminate consists of resin encapsulated fibres arranged in a preform. A composite preform is defined as the unconsolidated assemblage of dry fibres, yarns, and/or fabrics [5]. The design of a composite preform is by far a trivial task, and involves many different engineering and non-engineering aspects and disciplines. A simplified interaction scheme showing the key elements regarding the preform design process is presented in Fig. 2.

In order to design a suitable preform used for wind turbine blades, one must be aware of all the elements mentioned in Fig. 2. It is noted that the elements in the design process are interconnected in a non-coherent manner. For instance, choosing a certain filament diameter affects mechanical and processing properties. Therefore, the interaction scheme presented in Fig. 2 is iterative during the design process, and requires control of all the different elements. The preform must also be designed according to a number of business and regulation requirements, e.g. cost and a certain required strength (safety and reliability). The general requirements for future composites used in wind turbine blades are, [2]: enhanced mechanical properties (especially stiffness and fatigue), improved processing time, lower (or at least similar) cost as conventional fabrics, and improved reliability. In turn, a given preform must be designed to meet these requirements.

The present paper addresses the key elements of Fig. 2, and is limited to an introduction and discussion of the key elements related to the preform design for wind turbine rotor blades.

Figure 2: Interaction scheme with key elements and associated influential factors for consideration in the design of a composite preform for wind turbine blades. The key elements are encircled by an ellipse, and selected influential factors are mentioned in connection to these, [4].

1.1 Company profile

Danish based LM Wind Power is the world’s largest independent supplier of wind turbine rotor blades, operating 13 manufacturing facilities in China, India, Poland, Spain, Denmark, US, Canada and Brazil. With 5-7 new blade developments a year and a long list of records and patents, innovation is one of the key attributes of LM Wind Power which has technology hubs in Denmark, The Netherlands and India. LM Wind Power designs and builds blades that are optimized to the remaining parts of the turbine with the aim of finding the optimum balance between performance, reliability and cost. All designs are validated and tested beyond requirements in the company’s in-house wind tunnel and full scale testing facilities. The current product portfolio includes blades up to 73.5 meters length.

LM Wind Power specializes in the full range of disciplines within rotor blade development and composites technology from aerodynamics, blade construction, materials and manufacturing processes to full-scale testing. The company employs more than 300 engineers and is continuously expanding and looking for more skilled engineers to meet the increased demand for innovative rotor solutions that boost energy performance and reduce cost of energy. During the past 35 years, LM Wind Power has produced more than 175,000 blades since 1978 and almost one in four wind turbines installed worldwide have LM Wind Power blades.

2 MANUFACTURING CONCEPTS

Throughout the years, the different blade manufacturers have developed their own material technology and blade concept with the final aim of mastering both material and process to perfection. In general; however, the blade concept is the same: an outer aerodynamic profile for creating lift and a load-carrying composite structure within for carrying the loads. The difference from manufacturer to manufacturer basically lies in what is ‘under the hood’, i.e. load-carrying elements, sandwich materials, lightning protection system, and root solution. A generic blade is presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Sketch of a wind turbine rotor blade along with main components. (a) Overview. (b) Cross-section.

Different blade manufacturers have their own master technology, and the primary blade concepts are shown in Fig. 4 along with blade manufacturer’s baseline concepts and materials in Table 1.

Figure 4: Blade design concepts. (a) Single shear web. (b) Double shear web. (c) Box girder, [3].

The single shear web solution, Fig. 4(a), is rarely seen for large blades due to the relative low torsional stiffness compared with the closed concepts. The double shear web solution, Fig. 4(b), has the load-carrying main laminate within the aerodynamic shells whereas the box girder, Fig. 4(c), is a closed cross-section with thin aero dynamic profiles. The various concepts have different pros and cons with respect to mechanical resistance, blade performance, manufacturing process, cost, labour time, design freedom, structural reliability, etc.

Manufacturer	Fibre (main laminate)	Resin	Blade concept
LM Wind Power	Glass	Polyester	Shell assembly
Siemens Wind Power	Glass	Epoxy	Integral blade
Vestas	Carbon/glass	Epoxy	Box girder
TPI Composites	Glass (carbon)	Epoxy	Shell assembly
Euros	Glass (carbon)	Epoxy	Shell assembly
SSP Technology	Glass (carbon)	Epoxy	Box girder

Table 1: Blade manufacturer’s concept and material selection for the main laminate.

3 BASIC RELIABILITY CONCEPTS

Fig. 5 shows the design space available in order to avoid component/material failure (which may be considered as the reliability margin), in basic: material strength larger than the applied stress (load).

Figure 5: Sketch of the material design space available for composite material used in wind turbine rotor blades.

In order to reduce the probability of material failure, the stress and strength distributions should be separated as far as possible (increasing the design margin). Nonetheless, if the distributions are far apart, the material design is conservative. The distributions can be separated by translation or change of shape. In relation to the material stress, it is difficult to change the shape of the distribution due to the coupling to the random nature of the wind acting on the blade. However, there are two ways to translate the stress distribution in order to reduce the load: either by adding material to the component, or by improved smart component design. The first option is the obvious, but adds unwanted additional weight and cost to the component. The latter requires an optimisation of the structure, and can be beneficial in the long term. In any case, changing the location of stress distribution is a difficult task. On the other hand, the strength distribution can both change shape and location. A translation is achieved by materials with improved mechanical properties, which may add additional cost and save weight. The shape of the strength distribution can be altered by improved material understanding to reduce the material variability and increase the reliability.

Structural reliability is typically illustrated using the bath tub curve, exemplified in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Reliability bath tub curve of wind turbine blade.

The structural or material reliability is governed by three regimes:

I: Infant mortality with high failure rate during the first years of service. This is typically caused by manufacturing defects, wrong installation and operating conditions, or other issues.

New products are exposed to failure in this regime, and it is desired to reduce the failure rate as much as possible.

II: The governing part of the service life, say 80%, with low occurrence of failure. Failures in this regime are typically the stress exceeding the strength (c.f. Fig. 5).

III: Wear-out period when the structure approaches the end of the designed life-time (fatigue failure). For rotor blades; however, limited information is valid in this regime due to lack of field data and low number of running turbines.

All things considered, it is wanted to flatten out and lower the bathtub as much as possible.

4 DESIGN OF A COMPOSITE PREFORM

With emphasis on design and reliability, this section presents the underlying considerations presented in Fig. 2.

4.1 Material

The traditional baseline material selection for fibres used in wind turbine rotor blades is glass, which has been used since the early days of blade manufacturing. In recent years as blades are getting longer (c.f. Fig. 1), the need for a stiffer and stronger fibre material has emerged. Carbon is the most obvious choice, but the increase in mechanical performance compared with glass needs to be balanced with the additional cost, [4]. Hybrid materials (intelligent combinations of both glass and carbon) where the best properties from each material are utilised, are coming into play. However, more research and knowledge are required on hybrid composites before the material can enter as a common material for blade use. The most obvious candidate for additional fibre materials is natural fibres, and an instructive comparison between natural, glass, and carbon fibre materials, is shown in Table 2. Table 2 serves as an instructive indication and comparison of the various materials since there exists different material grades within each category.

	Natural fibres	Glass fibres	Carbon fibres
Density	Low	High	Moderate
Stiffness	Low	Moderate	High
Tensile strength	Low	Moderate	High
Compression strength	Low	High	Moderate
Fatigue resistance	Moderate/high	Moderate/high	High
Cost	Low	Low/moderate	High
Energy consumption	Low	Moderate	High
Renewability	Yes	No	No
Recyclability	Yes	No	No
Accessibility	High	High	Moderate
Distribution	Moderate	Wide	Moderate
Disposal	Degradable	Non-degradable	Non-degradable

Table 2: Instructive comparison between different fibre materials, [4].

4.2 Filament

A filament is the smallest unit of a fibrous material, and is often referred to as a fibre. Fibres are used rather than particles due to the blade manufacturing process and the fact that fibres can redistribute the load if a filament fails. In order to improve the fibre surface topology, increase the adhesion between fibre and resin, reduce the risk of moisture ingress, and improve wetting with the resin, the glass fibres

are sized with a silane based solution before they are collected in the roving. The sizing is chemically modified to suit a specific resin type (polyester, epoxy, etc.). The roving can either consist of twisted or un-twisted filaments (twisted rovings are often referred to as a yarn), but since fibre waviness reduces the compression strength of the composite, un-twisted rovings are the most widespread. Yarns (twisted rovings) are often employed when dealing with natural fibres whereas un-twisted rovings are used for carbon or glass. An example of a roving along with a non-crimp fabric is shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Example of roving and non-crimp fabric.

The size of the roving or bundle is classified as the linear density (mass per unit length, unit of tex [g / km]). The linear density affects different properties, e.g. drapeability, resulting preform thickness, wetting and permeability, and lay-up time. Larger fibre bundles reduce the drapeability, wetting properties, and the lay-up time, but the increased thickness is critical concerning intralaminar properties such as delamination.

4.3 Architecture

In order to position the glass fibres in the blade mould, the fibre bundles must be assembled in a given architecture which defines the type of preform (unidirectional, biaxial, triaxial, etc.). For application in wind turbine blades, 2D preforms offer the best characteristics when balanced between cost, processing, and mechanical performance. The optimum for the fibre architecture with regards to the application is achieved by non-woven preforms where the fibres are straight with low crimp. Fibres are arranged in straight bundles that are held together using a thread or glue, and these preform types are referred to as non-crimp fabrics (NCF's), see example in Fig. 7. Issues in relation to the design of NCF's are: size and shape of the bundles, number of filaments in the bundle, stitching tension applied to the bundles during the knitting process, knitting pattern, and the methodology for stabilising the preform, e.g. backing fibres, chop, or tackifier. The cost of NCF's is relatively low, and they offer a fine drapeability and permeability compared to woven preforms.

4.4 Mechanical properties

When the architecture of the preform is in place, the processed properties of the composite should be evaluated. However, the mechanical properties should still be considered and kept in mind in the previous stages of the preform design phase. Mechanical properties of the processed preform are decisive with regard to the application, and it is evident that the material resists the actions without failure. The average tension strain level due to the applied actions on a turbine blade is relatively low (often <1.0%, [3]), and therefore strength issues are in general not of major concern. In compression; however, material instability might be prevailing. Expansion due to moisture ingress or by temperature

fluctuations are also to be evaluated as a part of the mechanical considerations during the fabric design phase. Independent of the baseline material used the composite needs to sustain the given action with a certain margin of safety as prescribed by the certifying agencies. For larger blades (say >40 m), the blade design is generally based on primarily two factors, [1]:

- Tower clearance of the blade (stiffness driven design).
- Life-time of the blade (fatigue resistance).

Stiffness can be altered by changing the baseline material (see e.g. Table 2) or by adding layers to the composite. Fatigue resistance can be improved by a better material understanding, or by lowering the actions on the material (e.g. by smart design, or by adding layers in the laminate – which in turn will increase the blade weight). Blades are typically designed for a 20 years lifetime and will be exposed to more than 10^8 to 10^9 load cycles during the lifetime [1]. Thus, there is a need for a fatigue resistant and reliable material. Stiffness and static properties are primarily affected by the amount and individual properties of the filaments, whereas fatigue is closely related to the architecture

4.5 Processing

It is important that the preform can be processed in a reasonable time that allows for fast manufacturing of the structure. It is therefore required to have a high permeability and, at the same time, ensure a sufficient wetting between fibre and resin. The wetting is affected by the choice of sizing, but information on sizing properties is often kept confidential by the glass fibre manufacturers. The permeability is linked to the size (tex value) and shape of the fibre bundles, compaction of the bundles due to the stitching tension, intermediate bundle distance (see Fig. 8), and the architecture of the attached transverse layer. Infusion of a blade shell typically happens perpendicular to the warp direction of the preform, and a sketch of the infusion process is seen in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Transverse cross-section of the vacuum infusion process in a single-layered non-crimp fabric with a stabilising backing layer.

As illustrated in Fig. 8, the resin flow front is moving in the channels in-between the axial bundles and in the intermediate region between the transverse bundles. The inter-bundle saturation happens as the flow front passes by, but if the axial bundles are too large for the resin to enter due to the loss of pressure, there is a risk of dry glass within the bundle. This fact should be taken into account when determining the proper linear density and shape of the axial bundles. The intermediate bundle distance is important to ensure proper wetting along the axial fibre direction

4.6 Quality

For a blade manufacturer's perspective, the preform is designed according to the above mentioned key elements, and it is essential that the end product meet the expectations set by the blade manufacturer. In order to achieve the requested product quality, the blade manufacturer set up different demands in relation to the preform quality, e.g. straightness, size and extend of allowable defects, formability,

shelf-life, etc. Deficiencies and defect in the preform must be prevented, which require a certain quality control. This quality control implies standardised procedures for inspection of incoming preforms as well as methods for evaluation of the quality. At present, this is left to the consumer of the preform to evaluate the quality, and quality standards might be a way for improving the interaction between supplier and customer.

4.7 Certification

There is a number of certifying agencies dealing with the overall design of wind turbine blades. The most relevant of these are, along with the respective standard:

- Det Norske Veritas (DNV) [6].
- International Electrotechnical Commission [7].
- Germanischer Lloyd [8].

These standards are mostly engaged with the processed properties of the preform for blade design purposes, e.g. statistical variation and design values for strength, stiffness, and fatigue. Since these parameters are indirectly functions of the preform design, it is worth keeping them in mind during the preform design process. A recent merger between DNV and GL is believed to be setting the scene for future blades and blade materials to come.

5 CONCLUSIONS

It is a complex and challenging task to design a composite preform for a wind turbine rotor blade. The design involves many different iterative steps that are joint together in a non-coherent manner. The pre-design of a fabric can be made based on experience and knowledge e.g. regarding failure modes, manufacturing technology, and processing. However, in order to manufacture, test, certify, and implement a new fabric, many different stakeholders need to be involved. The stakeholders all have different approaches and interests in making the ultimate preform, but it is a balance between numerous factors.

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